

1 **06.06.2025, Sorbonne**

2 **Interviewee: Leonardo Caporarello**

3 **Interviewer: Filippo Martini**

4 **S01:** I'd like to start by asking you to tell us a bit about yourself before
5 we get into the first question. Leonardo Caporarello, if you agree, we can
6 proceed with the recording.

7 **S00:** Very well, I agree, yes, of course.

8 **S01:** Let me explain briefly what we'll do with this recording. The idea is
9 to conduct a qualitative analysis of the interviews. We've selected a few
10 of the panelists who seemed particularly interesting to us. The goal is to
11 gather different perspectives from these panelists — who may be
12 practitioners or, as in your case, academics — and to understand what you
13 actually do and how you view negotiation. So, returning to your role, I'd
14 like to ask you to tell us a bit about how you experience negotiation — in
15 other words, what you do in the field of negotiation.

16 **S00:** All right, thank you, Filippo, first of all, thanks for this
17 opportunity and for this conversation. Whatever comes out of it, I'm
18 already glad to take part.

19 I work both in the academic sphere and in the managerial one. From an
20 academic standpoint, within my institution, I'm a Professor of Practice of
21 Leadership and Negotiation, using a global perspective as my main lens of
22 analysis. Specifically, managing internal and external stakeholders with
23 the aim of reaching a shared decision - for example, regarding
24 organizational change, a new business partnership, or conducting a
25 diplomatic conversation.

26 Then, alongside that, there's the more managerial sphere. For about ten
27 years now, I've been serving as the Rector's Delegate for Digital Learning
28 — in Italian we'd say *Delegato del Rettore* — and Director of BUILT (Center
29 of Innovation in Teaching and Learning) at Università Bocconi, and more
30 recently, I've also been acting as Associate Dean for Online Learning
31 Experiences at SDA Bocconi School of Management. In these roles, I act as
32 an enabler and facilitator of innovation in teaching and learning models
33 and methods. This also includes the "execution side": turning ideas into
34 practice, something I truly enjoy.

35 That said, it should be clear that there are numerous discussions and
36 debates about how to explore new opportunities while continuing to exploit
37 existing ones. These conversations involve a variety of stakeholders,
38 diverse in background, competences, seniority, and experience. In other
39 words, there is a lot of negotiation.

40 **S01:** Yes, we say that everything is negotiation, according to some
41 perspectives — although I think that's a bit of an exaggeration. But even
42 teaching, in a certain sense, is a negotiation relationship.

43 **S00:** You're managing a relationship, because you have to convey value.
44 So,
45 fundamentally, from a theoretical point of view, you can trace it back to
the definition of negotiation — it's not a minor point, actually it's quite

46 a significant one.

47 When teaching, we have to be well prepared in communicating effectively:
48 conveying our message clearly and adjusting it to the audience we are
49 addressing . That's something we also do when negotiating. In this sense,
50 teaching is a great opportunity to practice this aspect of negotiation.

51 **S01:** Right, you could reconstruct or deconstruct it under a negotiation
52 lens, to understand who they are.

53 **S00:** Exactly — *profiling*, knowing who's in front of you.

54 **S01:** Yes, exactly. Because even from the perspective of position and
55 interest, you have to be able to understand who's sitting across from you —
56 that's a classic step.

57 **S00:** Right, because maybe they have no particular interest in the topic
58 you're teaching — and so, you see, somehow...

59 **S01:** Yes, so...

60 **S00:** These dynamics are true also in the abovementioned managerial
61 sphere.
62 Along with limited resources, e.g. time and budget, like in any managerial
63 role, you have to set up an organization with clear short- and long-term
64 goals, hiring the most talented people, defining projects' pipeline,
65 managing all the collaborators (internal and external to the project team),
66 interacting within and outside the project team and so on. So, technically
67 speaking, I deal with quite a range of stakeholders — it's a truly
68 multilateral negotiation context.

69 **S01:** Of course, so it's also a kind of *internal* negotiation — those are
70 often the most delicate ones.

71 **S00:** Absolutely. Being effective enough in presenting the value of
72 something "new" is always a challenge. It's nothing new in the literature,
73 actually it's part of any change management process. And this is why
74 negotiation skills are so important in this context, just because it's a
75 change process itself. Luckily, with my colleagues (faculty and staff
76 members) we have very good conversations — that's something I really
77 appreciate. So yes, it's a multilateral setting, characterized by a high
78 level of heterogeneity which, in turn, represents a great source of
79 creativity. Thus, we have to be prepared to deal with such a complex
80 context.

81 **S01:** Good. I'd like to move directly to the second question, if that's all
82 right with you. I'd like to focus on some of the themes that have been
83 discussed, both in a narrow and broad sense, during this conference.
84 Specifically, how Europe is dealing with certain issues and profound
85 transformations — social, political... There are pressures linked to
86 transnational dynamics in a broad sense, including terms we had almost
87 forgotten — like war — as well as political pressures related to climate
88 issues. So, there are different arenas that can be perceived as "hot topics,
89 " in a way. From your point of view, which of these changes — since we
90 perceive them as evolutionary changes — do you think has had the greatest
impact on negotiation today within the EU context?

..1.1. Geopolitical

91 **S00:** Russia-Ukraine conflict is one of the most significant in the last 4
92 years now, together with the most recent conflict in the middle east area.
93 Cases like these ones generate lots of uncertainty in the society, and when
94 facing such uncertainty unity and cohesion are key factors. Yet we keep
95 showing up as quite fragmented.

96 And this has a cost for all of us: not just in economic terms, but in
97 stress, anxiety, demotivation, thus confusion and disorientation.

..1.3. Climate

98 Then, there are other phenomena that have a *less* apparent impact for
99 some people — for example, climate change. This, in fact, has *devastating*
100 effects that we can literally *see* and *feel*. Yet some still tend to think of
101 it as something that will happen “later on.” And this short-termism doesn’t
102 help us either. For example, over the next thirty years, many high-mountain
103 glaciers may thin by several meters (in some cases exceeding three meters
104 of ice thickness loss), a scale of change that should give us pause.
105 Although it is expected many years from now, we get to act now in order to
106 prevent and reduce this risk.

107 **S01:** I’d say that, in a sense, you’ve already answered the next question,
108 which was about the challenges for the future. So, it seems to me that
109 fragmentation is one of those challenges — and yes, the short-term
110 mindset as well.

..5.1. Essential Skills a

111 **S00:** Exactly. Those two, if I had to summarize — and thank you for putting
112 it that way — would be at the top of my list. Although we can say, at a
113 general level, we are all aware of the relevance of these topics, the real
114 question is “to what extent do we genuinely need to be better prepared
115 for?”

116 First, awareness of challenges and issues; second, being effectively
117 prepared to face them.

118 **S01:** I’d say that we’ll come back to that in a little while, with another
119 question. But before that, I’d like to ask your personal perspective —
120 based on your experience — about a negotiation that you found particularly
121 challenging, maybe the most challenging one, and what made it so.

122 **S00:** Hmm, yes, I do have a situation in mind. The dynamic is basically the
123 following: a *multilateral* and complex kind of negotiation. Beyond levels of
124 competence, background and experience, negotiating parties were of
125 different age. And while that’s not an issue for me, some people look at
126 you — being younger — and think, “Well, what could you possibly know on
127 that matter?”

..3.1. Case Description

128 Behind this question, there may be some bias or assumptions, for instance,
129 the younger party is necessarily less prepared. Suppose person A has 10
130 years of experience and person B has 20 years in the same field. Although
131 person A has less experience than person B, this does not necessarily
132 mean

132 that A is less prepared for a specific negotiation topic: A might be
133 equally or even better prepared.

134 Second, something I discovered gradually: some of the participants at the
135 table had a *prior relationship* that I hadn’t known about beforehand. I

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realized it only as the meeting went on — when arrows started flying and certain sarcastic remarks made it clear that some people were still settling old scores from three years earlier!

Thus, a negotiation – already complex because of differing interests, values, and constituencies – can become even more *complicated* – because of e.g. bias, prior relationships, unsettled scores among the parties, ego –, and this is a major challenge for negotiators.

S01: I think the problem is that doing it yourself is very difficult. You can train yourself to do it, but the moment the other party isn't able to do it, you end up having to do double the work. And in a multilateral negotiation, that multiplies by n , depending on how many people are at the table.

S00: Negotiations can be either complex or complicated, but complex doesn't necessarily mean complicated. In the first case, we can apply the principle of *equal complexity: dealing with a complex negotiation requires equally complex preparation. A negotiation, however, becomes complicated usually because of unmanaged emotional reactions.*

S01: That's very interesting — in multilateral negotiations, coalitions often form before the parties even sit at the table. But I can imagine that realizing this during the negotiation, when you might have known it in advance during the *intelligence phase*, can be tricky.

S00: If you haven't managed to figure it out in advance, then you have to rely on your improvisation skills. *Improvisation*, one of a good negotiator's key skills, helps you deal with the unexpected: stop arguing, discover, understand, adapt, act.

S01: I really like that idea of *stopping* — because it's something that, in my limited experience, people often struggle to do. Once you're there, there's this pressure to reach an agreement, so the idea of stopping, stepping back, and returning to the preparation phase isn't so intuitive.

S00: No, no, not at all. It's not easy.

S01: Very interesting approach — I have to say, I'll take that lesson with me personally.

S00: Thank you — try it out and let me know! But yes, I honestly find it very useful myself.

S01: All right, let's go back to some recommendations. Do you have any recommendations that eventually led to reaching an agreement?

S00: As we always say, "the power of the break." It sounds a simple concept, but it's incredibly powerful. It's a moment to reflect, to do a quick micro-review: *What's going on? What may need to be adjusted?* Then, you recalibrate and re-prepare.

And, if we are negotiating in teams, always remember to leverage

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..4.1. Research / Practi | 188

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..3.1.1. Challenges | 212

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..4.3. Bridging Strat | 220

teamwork:
role play within the team, exploit their skills and capabilities.

S01: Very interesting. This idea of taking a pause in multilateral negotiations seems less common than in bilateral ones, where there's the classic idea of stepping back to realign. In a multilateral setting, it seems much more complex — and more interesting.

Staying with the conference theme — which is about building connections, the idea of multidisciplinary — and also the journal's theme, bridging the academic side and the practitioner side (those who work on training in corporate or organizational contexts more broadly), I'd like to ask: where do you see the biggest *gap* between academia and those who *practice* negotiation?

S00: Well, education first. I mean, looking at the global landscape, negotiation training at the higher education level is not enough. Sometimes there are short courses, or small modules within larger courses. But there aren't many dedicated learning units focused specifically on *developing negotiation skills*.

Recently, the need for learning negotiation skills is steadily increasing. But, for example, I remember that about ten years ago, it wasn't very common topic, in Italy as well as in many other countries. And I do not mean that higher education institutions must necessarily create ad-hoc courses on negotiation. As negotiation is a behavioral competence/science, integrating negotiation skills with other topics would work perfectly. This would fit very well in an interdisciplinary framework.

For example, when finance managers discuss a quarterly budget revision with line managers, they are actually negotiating. Or, when production managers are discussing with procurement colleagues because they need faster delivery conditions from their suppliers, they are negotiating. Basically, we do negotiate much more often than expected, at any level of seniority, any industry, any context.

Thus, having a robust methodological framework to support negotiation processes is essential.

S01: It seems to me that this brings us back to that basic dimension of *awareness*. To use the metaphor of the glass being half full or half empty — we first need to be aware that the glass is half empty, before we can fill it. So perhaps this connects with what you were saying earlier.

S00: Yes, yes, very much so — exactly. Unfortunately, though, that awareness is often missing.

S01: Let me ask you — in your opinion, how could civil society actors be involved in bridging this gap?

S00: Well, through discussion, debating, learning — first of all. Probably those who have the power to *document* things should take the lead. In this landscape, Schools have a major responsibility in this process. Through research we can analyze the phenomenon, collect cases and experiences, make publications to share the know-how and teach to our learners. AI can act as

..4.3. Bridging Strateg | 221

a booster to make the set of situations as broad and accessible as possible.

..3.1.1. Challenges

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I was just saying this in a panel earlier today — a colleague asked: "Why don't organizations even *think* about negotiation?" Because they relate the concept of negotiation often with *sales* or *purchasing processes*. While these are good examples of negotiation, that's not all.

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It's also a responsibility of every single individual. Whatever is our role within institutions or organizations, we should ask ourselves "how do I negotiate?". The question is not "if" rather "how" we do that.

..4.2. Civil Society & N

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If I could dream a little, I'd say: every citizen, in any organization or institution, should be able to *understand* — which is the step forward awareness. Dissemination and continuous learning become significant.

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Whether you're a team coordinator, a manager, a department director, or a head of business unit — anyone who deals with people — should be able to negotiate.

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S01: So, bringing a dimension of personal awareness into the professional realm as well — if I can summarize that with another framework.

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S00: In a way, yes — exactly. Starting from the personal level, where you internalize it, and then transferring it.

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S01: That could also allow us to make a kind of *mindset shift*: from what is often a naturally *competitive* negotiation toward a more *collaborative* one.

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S00: Exactly.

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S01: Which would, of course, allow us to grow — not only as individuals but also collectively, as a society. Coming back to the conference theme — there's something I'd like to ask you, also in connection with the abstract you kindly shared with me. Since we're at the *European Negotiation Conference*, regarding the "European" aspect — do you think negotiation in Europe differs systematically from other regions? In other words, let's address the issue of the *cultural factor*. I know you've already touched on this a bit, but I'd like to hear your view.

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S00: If you ask people who Jean Monnet was — in many European countries...

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(I've had the honor of giving an executive course in his home just outside Paris, and I was almost moved to tears.)... unfortunately, I don't know how many could tell you who he was.

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For me, it's inconceivable that someone dealing with negotiation doesn't know who Jean Monnet is. This is part of our history and background in negotiation.

..2.1. European

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So, there's a strong diversity across the 27 countries in terms of educational preparation on negotiation — from primary to higher education.

..2.2. Non-European

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Such diversity is also outside Europe, of course. Some countries, and in particular some higher education institutions (e.g. in North America), invest more systematically in developing this competence. So yes, there are clear differences in the degree of awareness and preparation on

..2.2. Non-European

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negotiation phenomenon.

..2.1. European

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S01: So it seems, in a sense, that Europe lacks homogeneity – which connects again to the earlier theme of fragmentation. These are issues that resurface both at the *micro* level, within organizations, and at the *macro* level.

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S00: I like to see it as a whole — it's *holistic*, isn't it? But yes, that's exactly how it is.

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S01: Going back to the idea of training — in your opinion, what are the key skills for a negotiator today and tomorrow?

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..5.1. Essential Skill:

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S00: Today and tomorrow. Other than the obvious ones, I'd strongly emphasize *creative thinking* or, more broadly, *creativity*. Here's the backbone: moving increasingly toward *integrative negotiation*, we need flexibility. And you can't be flexible if you're afraid to get out of the comfort zone. The risk is that the longer our experience, the less flexible we become.

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..5.1. Essential Skills a

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Leveraging *creativity* allows us to explore what we don't yet know, or even what *we know we don't know*, without fear of the unknown. This is the path towards a more truly collaborative approach.

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Alongside that, studying to better understand *cultural differences*. It's something not new, and we're witnessing it in our everyday life. Thus, being flexible includes readiness to adapt our negotiation techniques to the specific cultural context. It isn't a one-size-fits-all approach: negotiating with someone belonging to Italian or Vietnamese culture may require very different use of techniques. It is as basic as it is essential.

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S01: So on the one hand, you're talking about the capacity for personal *intelligence*...

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S00: Yes, and we should avoid jumping too quickly to conclusions, while we must profile, study differences and what characterizes each of us. Not to judge who's better, worse, or nicer – but simply to understand what defines us.

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S01: So a view that's not evaluative, but clearly descriptive.

..5.1. Essential Skills a

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S00: Exactly – I must not evaluate your way of speaking, gesturing, or using nonverbal cues as "I like it" or "I don't like it." I should only *decode* and interpret, for instance, that your head movement could mean A, B, or C — for the instrumental purpose of reaching a peaceful agreement.

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S01: How would you introduce these new skills into a training program?

..5.3. Teaching Method

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S00: "Very easily". There are many real-world cases and examples of negotiation in different disciplines, and context. So, let's also discuss them within our courses. It would be a valuable first step for increasing *awareness*.

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As mentioned earlier, for instance, whether it's a degree in political science or a specialized course in macroeconomics, at some point you have

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305 to sit down with other colleagues to write a regulation, a rule, or a
306 memorandum of understanding. In all these cases – and, in general, where
307 two or more people interact to discuss the possibility of a shared decision
308 – it becomes a negotiation process.

309 **S01:** Right – so, including this aspect in education actually seems like the
310 easier part. I mean, introducing creative thinking and awareness of
311 cultural differences into training seems simpler, from my point of view,
312 than teaching a practical negotiation tool. Yes, I'd agree with you: the
313 awareness part is easier to integrate.

..5.1. Essential Skills a

314 **S00:** As I like to say, first comes *awareness and understanding*, and then
315 *applying*. That's the framework I use. So yes, that's step one, certainly.

316 **S01:** Well, then let's move toward the final questions. I'd like to ask:
317 what's one research or practical question that, in your view, still remains
318 unanswered?

..6.1. Research Question

319 **S00:** Hmm... well, *Generation Z*, and even more so *Generation Alpha* –
320 those
321 born from around 2013–2015 – will inevitably have a different style. Their
322 *learning style* has already changed, and consequently, their preferred
negotiation style may be different too.

323 So the question is: *how should I prepare myself to interact with them?* And
324 at the same time, *how should I teach them* to become good negotiators?

325 **S01:** That's really interesting. It seems that, in a way, this reconstructs
326 the training dynamic itself as a form of negotiation.

327 **S00:** Exactly.

328 **S01:** I really like that.

329 **S00:** Then, to close the loop, *emotions come into play*.

330 **S01:** All the best conversations start and end that way – in a circular
331 dynamic. So, I'd say we can conclude. I'd like to ask you, if you could, to
332 recommend one *film* and one *book* about negotiation.

333 **S00:** This question about the book makes me smile because, of course, I
334 couldn't help but think of my own. I would like to explain why I'm
335 mentioning it: "Let's Negotiate: bring your success to the next level"
336 (Bocconi University Press, 2025) is not just another book on negotiation,
337 it has built around a new concept: partly static and partly dynamic. As it
338 evolves over time, it offers a fresh reading each time.

339 That said, if we exclude the great classics – the ones everyone
immediately
340 thinks of – I would actually recommend a "*non-book*": a short report of
341 about forty pages called *The Zen of Negotiation*, published by Kent in 2024.
342 I like it because it has a different angle – less technical than manuals on
343 specific negotiation methods – and instead offers a broader reflection.

..5.1. Essential Skills a

344 The author talks about the importance of negotiating in a calm, safe
345 environment – *psychological safety* – to find collaborative solutions. As

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we've said several times, emotional management works much better in a serene atmosphere than in a tense or heated one.

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And as for films: there are the great classics, but I would like to go for something different: *Money Monster* – it was directed by Jodie Foster about ten years ago, in 2016. She did a great job, and George Clooney stars in it as well.

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The film tells the story of a journalist hosting a live TV show about finance, and at a certain point, a delivery worker bursts in and takes the host hostage. From there, the dynamics shift completely. Have you seen it?

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S01: I haven't, but I'll definitely watch it.

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S00: So yes — he's presenting live on air, and suddenly he's taken hostage. From there, a whole new dynamic unfolds — it's really interesting. It's much less known than *The Negotiator* or the other famous classics everyone

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knows.

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S01: I must admit, I haven't read *The Zen of Negotiation* either, so I'll make sure to check it out. I do know the film, but I haven't watched it yet. You've definitely given me a few ideas for the more entertaining side – so thank you very much, Leonardo.

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S00: It's truly been a wonderful interview — thank you so much as well for your time.